

ACTUAL ISSUES OF TRAINING LEGAL PSYCHOLOGISTS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The article discusses current issues facing the field of legal psychology. It describes the historical roots and theoretical and methodological foundations of legal psychology. The content of the structure of legal psychologist's professional authority is explained.*

Keywords: *psychology, legal psychology, professional skills, skills and qualifications of a legal psychologist, law, law, law enforcement agencies.*

It is known that in recent years the importance of legal psychology as an independent branch of psychology is increasing. This can be seen especially in areas such as investigative activities, prevention of terrorism, criminology, forensic psychology, and resolution of legal professional fitness issues.

Dissertation research is emerging in the field of legal psychology. Among them: V.G. Shepotkin (1994), E. Yu. Agzamova (2001), M.Kh. Akhmedova (2007); G.A. Normurodov (2008); H.T. Mahmudova (2009), I. Arifkhodjaeva (2011), B. Umarov (2011) and others can be acknowledged. S.V. Asyamov developed educational manuals such as "Professional-psychological training of employees of internal affairs bodies", "Psychological analysis of the emergency search situation and tactics of operations of operatives", "Psychological components of modern terrorism", "How a person should behave during the threat of terrorism" . However, studies on the psychology of judicial activity have not been reflected in scientific research until now, and no scientific research has been conducted by Uzbek psychologists [1].

Starting from the 2018/2019 academic year, the specialty line "Psychological support of service activity" was opened at the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and currently cadets are studying in this direction. This, of course, refers to the specialty of a legal psychologist. Nevertheless, there are many shortcomings and unsolved problems in the field of legal psychology in the conditions of Uzbekistan today.

First of all, it is necessary to consider the issue of general theoretical and methodological foundations of legal psychology. Undoubtedly, this draws our attention to, for example, Russian scientists V.L. Vasiliev, V.N. Volkov, M.I. Enikeev, G.Kh. Efremova, N.N. Smirnova, V.M. Pozdnyakov, A.R. Ratinov, V.V. Romanov, O.D. Sitkovskaya, A.M. Stolyarenko, Yu.V. Chufarovskiy, I.K. Shakhrianyan, G.G. Shikhantsov, S.I. Yanaev, V.F. Engalichev and others contribute to the wide field of legal psychology, which encourages us to focus on the methodological foundations [2].

Based on the study of the historical roots of legal psychology, we can see that a lot of research is devoted to forensic psychology. The analysis of scientific literature shows that its problems are closely related to practical requirements. These include: the psychology of interrogation, the psychology of trial participants, the psychology of the reliability of witness testimony, mental and psychological influence, etc. (O.A. Gavrillov, F.V. Glazirin, A.V. Dulov,

V.I. Goncharenko, V.G. Pushkov, F.M. Sokiran, Yu.I. Ilchenko, N.P. Khaydukov, D.S. Chizhova, etc.).

Great progress has been made in forensic psychological expertise. In this direction, V.V. Avramtsev, L.V. Alekseeva, E.V. Vasque, V.P. Kislyakov, M.M. Kochenov, L.P. Konisheva, S.L. Kopotev, M.V. Morozova, V.V. Nagaev, T.P. Pechernikova, F.S. Safuanov, T.V. Sakhnova, T.N. Sekeraj, O.D. Sitkovskaya, E.N. The scientific work of Kholopova, S.S. Shipshin, V.F. Engalichev and other scientists should be specially recognized.

Currently, a lot of work is being done in the field of criminal psychology. Scientific works of Y.M. Antonyan, A.G. Beloborodov, S.V. Borodin, V.V. Guldan, V.N. Kudryavtsev, T.N. Kurbatova, V.V. Luneev, B.D. Liskov, A.R. Ratinov, A.M. Yakovlev are an example of this.

Basics of military-legal psychology, which is a special field of legal psychology, by A.G. Karoyani, V.V. Romanov, A.M. It was developed and put into practice by scientists such as Stolyarenko, L.F. Zheleznyak. On the psychology of investigation and the psychology of rapid-search activity: V.E. Konovalova, D.V. Mironov, V.F. Moskalenko, S.S. Ovchinsky, E.G. Samovichev, M.P. Smirnov, Yu. V. Chufarovskiy. On the psychology of criminal responsibility: M.V. Kostitsky, G.M. Minkovsky, O. D. Sitkovskaya conducted research.

Considerable results were also achieved in the field of penitentiary psychology, in which A.V. Budanov, M.G. Debolsky, A.D. Glotchkin, N.S. Kravchun, V.F. Pirozhkov, A.V. Pishchenko, V.M. Pozdnyakov, M.P. Sturova, A.N. Sukhov, G.A. Tumanov's research work deserves special attention.

A large volume of work related to psychological properties, states and processes of legal importance is associated with in-depth research. Aggression and aggression (N.R. Ratinova, A.A. Rean, F.S. Safuanov, S.N. Enikolopov, etc.), hypnosis (L.P. Grimak, V.A. Danilov, A.B. Moshchansky, V.D. Khabalev, etc.), polygraph examination (S.N. Zerin, I.S. Zubrilova, Ya.V. Komissarova, V.V. Semyonov, A.I. Skripnikov, Yu.I. Kholodny, S.A. Yani, etc.), post-traumatic stress (I.O. Kotenyov, E.O. Lazebnaya, M.M. Reshetnikov, M.V. Tarabrina, E.M. Cherepanova, etc.) directions included.

Important results have been achieved in accordance with the psychological-acmeological approach for legal psychology related to the in-depth development of practical and methodological support for the professional development of a practicing psychologist, optimization of the entire process of professional skills (B.G. Ananov, K.A. Abulkhanova-Slavskaya, E.N. Bogdanov, A.A. Bodalev, A.A. Derkach, A.S. Guseva, V.G. Zazikin, N.V. Kuzmina, I.N. Semenov, A.P. Sitnikov, E.A. Yablokova and others.). Such an approach helps in the development of a new professional "I" based on previously formed criteria for evaluating the professional skills and labor productivity of a practicing psychologist.

Thus, legal psychology is considered a branch of general psychology and is a field with significant scientific potential related to the daily activities of many specialists and psychological support of law enforcement agencies.

When it comes to law enforcement activities with a psychological component, many authors have pointed out similar directions. For example, M.I. Enikeev - legal, criminological, investigative, judicial and correctional activities (2001), and A.M. Stolyarenko - criminological, organizational, management and personnel work (2001). Other authors have defined similar directions in terms of form and meaning.

There are seven types of law enforcement.

The first is legal activity, the main purpose of which is the legal regulation of human life as the main form of social order.

The second is criminological activity. This is a type of law enforcement activity that is related to studying the causes of crime, the conditions and forms of illegal activity (Tatarukhin, 2003).

The third is crime prevention, which is the most important direction in law enforcement activities. In this case, the case is not about specific violations, but directly about the causes of illegal actions and their prevention.

The fourth is the investigation of the crime, which focuses on collecting objective information, evidence and instructions, identifying the criminal and apprehending him [3].

The fifth is protection of human rights [4].

The sixth is the judicial activity, which is considered the central part.

The seventh is correctional activity. Its main goal is to restore previously damaged individual psychological characteristics necessary for a person's full life in society.

It should be noted that each type of law enforcement activity listed above has its own psychological component and is characterized by psychological processes, laws and phenomena of a specific type.

V.F. Engalichev [5] distinguishes eight areas of legal psychology related to the work of law enforcement agencies and groups them into three blocks. *The first block* includes legal and criminal psychology, which defines the methodology of legal psychology. The remaining five fields are included in the *second block*, and the psychology of the law enforcement organization is included in the *third block*.

G.G. Shikhantsov describes the "structural organization" or "category system" of legal psychology [6]. As elements of this system, the author distinguished the following:

- 1) methodological section, which includes the subject, tasks, system, methods and history of development of legal psychology;
- 2) legal psychology;
- 3) criminal psychology;
- 4) investigative psychology;
- 5) forensic psychology;
- 6) correctional psychology.

At the same time, V.M. Pozdnyakov suggests not to divide legal psychology into departments. According to him [7], "it should include not only determining the boundaries of established departments, but also forming new ones, the structure of legal psychology as a science, the study of psychological phenomenology of objects, subjects and the composition of law enforcement agencies."

In the practical application of this direction, according to the author, "not only structural, but also functional and genetic analysis" should be used along with a systematic approach to describe the components of legal psychology. In this V.M. Pozdnyakov created a tree-like description of legal psychology (see scheme 1) [7].

The author states that "*first*, as in a living natural tree, here too one can see a dialectical, organic evolutionary relationship between all its parts and the surrounding world. *Secondly*, if we artificially "visually" look at any part of this "tree", we will find the general similarity of all its subsystems... *Thirdly*, the presence of numerous "gaps" and individual buds in the "tree of legal

psychology" indicates that its capabilities are still not significantly actualized. Currently, these include the psychology of private and business law, psychological problems of law-making by collective subjects, court proceedings in civil cases, and many promising directions in the development of foreign legal psychology can be considered as a continuation of the ideas presented by V.M. Pozdnyakov.

Drawing 1. Genetic-structural structure of legal psychology

Here: ① – conditions of legal psychology, ○ – subsystems, ◐ – its directions. 1 – philosophy; 2 – general psychology; 3 – social psychology; 4 – legal sciences; 5 – humanitarian sciences; 6 – natural and technical sciences; 7 – applied psychological sciences; 8 - methodological foundations of methodological-theoretical psychology; 9 – legal psychology; 10 – criminal psychology; 11 – psychology of judicial activity in criminal cases; 12 – psychology of civil-law regulation and civil court proceedings; 13 - psychology of investigation and rapid search activity; 14 - psychology of the work of special divisions of the Department of Internal Affairs; 15 – military-legal psychology; 16 – penitentiary psychology; 17 – psychology of law making; 18 – psychology of a criminal; 19 – psychology of criminal groups; 20 – psychology of the victim; 21 – psychology of judicial activity; 22 - psychology of the prosecutor's work; 23 – psychology of lawyer activity; 24 – board psychology; 25 – forensic psychological expertise in criminal cases; 26 - judicial psychological expertise in civil cases; 27 – psychology of the arbitration court; 28 – psychology of firefighters; 29 - psychology of the work of yhh employees; 30 - psychology of special forces activity; 31 – preventive psychology.

In the process of reforms aimed at legal psychology in our country, it is necessary to pay attention to its theoretical-methodological, organizational and practical problems, and in the process of training legal psychology specialists, there are many aspects that have not been studied in our conditions. Legal psychologists (specialists of psychological provision of services) can be directed to the profession only by clearly differentiating their professional knowledge and practical skills.

Thus, for our country, we have before us the training of specialists who know the historical roots of legal psychology, who perfectly study and apply foreign experience and theoretical and

methodological bases, meet the requirements of the time, as well as carry out fundamental scientific and research work, both independent and integrative in the field of jurisdiction. as a science, there are urgent tasks to present it in a fundamental way.

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